

WAYS TO USE VIDEO IN THE CLASSROOM TO MAKE THE LESSONS MORE INTERACTIVE

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ABSTRACT

From centuries, teachers are always striving to make their lessons both informative and fun for the learners and to give them the best education. In this article, we will focus on some tips of using video in the classroom (auditorium) to entertain students and to make the learning fun.

Introduction. These days with the access to the Internet, smart phones or other electronic gadgets, it has been even easier to the teachers to get video into the classroom as a learning resource. Teachers can develop students' listening, speaking skills, language usage and improve their pronunciation in the target language. It can also be used to generate interactive classroom activities, so it's very versatile.

Using video in the classroom is useful for both teachers and learners. It allows students to learn at their own pace and free up time for teachers to support students' individually. In addition, video is one of the powerful tools to motivate students learning the foreign languages. From short video clips, flashbacks to full-length films like documentaries or movies, video helps students to engage in a topic, to understand new vocabulary, and to have an opportunity to listen to authentic English.

There are quite a lot of benefits that come from using videos during any classroom

and learning session. The main advantages in the use of video in the classroom are the following:

a) In today's education, informal learning is a meaningful part of our learning experience. Formal education no longer includes the majority of our learning. By using interactive video lessons teachers will keep pace with the digital world.

b) Technology is altering our brains. The tools we use define and shape our thinking. Choosing correct video tools encourage students to broaden their horizons and worldview.

c) Most movies and flashbacks are the reflection of our real life and taken from real situations. Teaching grammar rules with the help of video clips is not only interactive, but also communicative way of learning, that students will be able to use the language freely in the real world.

d) We know that students learn best when they take an information via multiple

modalities—through reading, drawing, listening to the teacher’s oral explanations, and viewing visual media. We also know, from much research, that using visuals is key for those acquiring a new language.

e) In an approach known as the “flipped classroom”, students may engage with video material at home before working through the issues in class. This benefits the students by allowing reinforcement of learning in a collaborative context and repeated watching of previous clips if considered necessary.

According to Courtney White and Min-ji Nam using video is an appropriate method of instruction for many goals of teaching and learning.

Some of these include:

- Minds-On/Hook
- Inspire
- Listening Skills
- Predicting
- Debate
- Interviewing Skills
- Comprehension
- Writing Prompt
- Information/Explanation
- Storytelling

Here are some suggestions for the teachers before playing the video in the classroom:

1. Be selective. Try to find a clip that corresponds roughly to the topic of the lesson. Be clear on your purpose and determine what do you intend to show and what do you expect from it.

2. Setting a task. In order to be sure your students actively watch, set a task before playing the video. For instance, “While watching, I want you to pay attention to” Setting a goal for what students are about to watch will keep them accountable and attentive.

3. The shorter the more effective. Keep videos short if you don’t want your students get bored. Six minutes is the absolute maximum, less for younger students. Data from massive open online courses [MOOCs] shows engagement drops off markedly after six minutes. If you really need to use longer video, break it into smaller parts or use pauses to make intervals and stimulate discussion.

One of the greatest benefits to using video in the classroom is the conversation that comes out of viewing an informative or enlightening piece. Research is showing that engaging students in discussion in the classroom helps them to better understand what they are learning.

Tips on how to use video in the language learning lessons:

1. Sound off

To get the students more interested in the video, the teacher turns the sound off and asks them to watch. After viewing students tell each other or to the teacher what they think the people in the video doing or what has happened by guessing the plot. Afterwards, the teacher plays the video with the sound on and they can see if they were right.

2. Image off

Teacher can also play the video with the screen covered or the image turned off. The students listen and predict what they think is showing on the screen. They can discuss their ideas in pairs or groups and then watch the video again with the images showing.

3. Numbering nouns in order

If the video consists of various objects in different places or going to somewhere, like in the shopping center or travelling scenes, write on the board the names of around 10 objects which appear. Write the

names randomly, mixing the names. The students watch the video and have to number the items in the order they see them. This is a useful task for reviewing previously-learnt vocabulary and for introducing a few new words.

4. Comprehension questions

For video with lots of speaking, such as narration, write a set of comprehension questions to help the students listen for certain key words or information and to check their understanding. You can use this activity for grammar lessons too. Ask the students to number tenses, nouns, adjectives or adverbs, types of sentences and other grammatical features that are used in the video. They make grammatical analysis of the clip they watched.

5. Using the video script

If you have a copy of the video script, there are several things you can do with it. You may leave gaps in particular words or expressions and have the pupils listen and write them. Alternatively, you may break the script into individual lines, mess them up, and have the learners sort them out as they watch.

6. Subtitle creation

Try the following challenge with a video that has subtitles that you can turn on or off, which is helpful for intensive listening. Choose a short video segment with text or dialogue (the length will depend on the quantity of words). Students should listen and take notes on what they hear. It's possible that you'll have to play it more than once. Students can compare and assist one another in between viewings. Finally, turn on the subtitles for the video. Students compare their transcriptions to the ones displayed on the screen.

7. Subtitle translation

Another variation of activity 6 works if you have a class where everyone speaks the same mother tongue and you have a video in their language which has the option of English subtitles. Play the video in their native tongue and tell them you'd like them to translate the words into English. Students view the video a few times before translating the text. Finally, they compare their versions with the English subtitles on the film.

8. Produce a video

It is incredibly simple for learners to create a video that they wrote and directed themselves. This may be a scripted play or a documentary about their hometown - the options are unlimited. The strength of making video is that it really motivates the students to work on their spoken English because they are appearing on the screen for other people to see.

9. Making a soundtrack

If you don't have the resources or time for your students to create their own video, you could take an existing video which shows images of a place or some simple documentary footage. If there is a soundtrack in the video, turn it off. Students work in groups and write their own stories while watching a video (several times). After completing the script, one student from each group plays the video and reads the new story. Finally, all groups read and listen to different narrations.

10. What happens next?

This activity goes well with a drama. Show a short section of the film with two or three characters. Afterwards, talk about what is happening and make sure everyone understands the plot so far. Then ask the students to work in groups and write the scene that they think will follow on from

what they have seen. If you have time, ask them to rehearse reading the new script or even performing it. Each group then reads or performs their scripts to the class. Afterwards, play the scene that actually follows in the original film for them to compare.

EXCELLENT SITES THAT SUPPLEMENT YOUR LESSONS

In addition to the YouTube channels that concentrate on concepts, you'll discover lots of channels that offer engaging and thought-provoking supplemental ideas that can complement the work you're doing in the classroom.

Videos from NOVA <http://www.pbs.org/> are produced showing the miracles of science;

inspirational TED Talks <http://www.youtube.com/user/TEDtalksDirector> on subjects ranging from sustainability to gender inequality;

behind-the-scenes views of the international space station on Reel NASA; <http://www.youtube.com/user/ReelNASA> a walk through the world's most impressive art collection at the Museum of Modern Art (MoMA)

<http://www.youtube.com/user/MoMAvideos> -- these are all part of the rich mix of content that gives students access to a world of subjects;

Smart Songs <http://www.youtube.com/user/smartsongs> combines hip hop, storytelling and skits to create memorable songs that explore history and science topics.

Students are likely to get catchy lyrics from raps like "Three Branches [of Government]," "Bill of Rights" and "Stock Market" stuck in their heads for days;

[Youtube.com/Teachers](http://www.youtube.com/user/teachers)

<http://www.youtube.com/user/teachers> saves time by identifying and organizing educational content aligned with the Common Core State Standards. Teachers can search by subject area - language arts, math, science and social studies, or by grade level - elementary, middle school and high school;

EduTube.org <http://www.edutube.org/> is an educational video search platform with helpful indexes that measure popularity, ranking and educational value. The objective is to create a more effective way to search YouTube videos for specific content;

Several of the featured schools include popular video collections like Khan Academy

<http://www.youtube.com/user/khanacademy>, a growing collection of video tutorials about math, science, humanities and art concepts.

In conclusion, videos offer an immersive, flexible, engaging, and stimulating experience, with the ability to integrate information in ways that are fun, entertaining, and easy to understand. If we truly want to obtain a better, more immersive and meaningful learning experience for our learners, then we should definitely consider using videos in the classroom.

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